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Research Article

**CLINICAL EFFICACY OF TRIMETAZIDINE (VESTRAL MR)
IN ACUTE MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION****Dr Anam Naz¹, Dr Shumaila Nasreen², Dr Muhammad Usman Afzal³**¹Foundation University Medical College, Islamabad, ²Nantong Medical University, China,³Benazir Bhutto Hospital, Rawalpindi.**Article Received:** July 2020**Accepted:** August 2020**Published:** September 2020**Abstract:****Introduction:** Coronary artery disease is the leading cause of death in the US, Europe and developed countries.**Objectives:** To evaluate the clinical benefit of using trimetazidine in acute MI with thrombolytic therapy. 100 patients with acute MI were enrolled in the study.**Patients and Methods:** This study was conducted in the Medical department of Holy Family Hospital and Benazir Bhutto Hospital Rawalpindi for six months duration from 1st November 2019 to 30th April 2020 on 100 patients meeting criteria for acute MI during this study.**Results:** One hundred patients were qualified to group I and group II (50 patients each). In group I, 50 patients were treated with thrombolytic therapy, i.e. with streptokinase alone. In group II, 50 patients were treated with streptokinase together with trimetazidine. These patients were followed up to the sixth month and complications such as arrhythmia, congestive heart failure, bleeding, re-infarction, angina and death were compared in both groups.**Key words:** Vestral MR, Acute MI, Trimetazidine.**Corresponding author:****Dr. Anam Naz,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Coronary artery disease is the leading cause of death in the US, Europe and developed countries. In 2001, CAD accounted for 54% of all deaths from cardiovascular disease and was one of the most common causes of death in the United States [1-2]. There are no such data for the Pakistani population. The epidemic of cardiovascular disease in developing countries was highlighted in a report by W.H.O. Nearly 85% of global mortality and the burden of cardiovascular disease occur in low- and middle-income countries such as Pakistan [3-4]. A 2003 population survey in Karachi, aged over 40, found an overall prevalence rate of 26.9% for men and 30% for women. Several studies have shown that mean mortality is around 2-3% per year, with a further 2-3% withstanding non-fatal MI [5-6]. The treatment option for acute MI available in our part of the world is thrombolytic therapy, more commonly streptokinase, PCI and By Pass surgery. In acute MI, central necrosis occurs, which is surrounded by a variable amount of viable but dysfunctional myocardium due to hypoxic-induced metabolic disturbances. In a normal, healthy state, the heart draws most of its energy, ie 2/3 from free fatty acid (FFA) and 1/3 from the oxidation of glucose and lactate. During hypoxia due to decreased blood supply, glucose uptake at the cellular level is reduced and conversion to lactate is increased, followed by cellular acidosis [7-8]. The FFA pathway is also slowed down and ATP production is reduced. These metabolic disturbances cause disruption of cell function and damage to the cell membrane, which eventually lead to arrhythmias, contractility failure, and electrophysiological abnormalities [9]. Therefore, if we can prevent the viable but dysfunctional myocardium around the necrotic myocardium, by adding agents that prevent the above metabolic disorders, such as a 3KAT inhibitor (trimetazidine) which increases glucose and lactate burning and prevents cell acidosis. In this way, complications during and after acute MI can be prevented. The present study assesses the clinical benefits of trimetazidine in acute MI along with thrombolytic therapy [10]. 100 patients with acute MI were enrolled in the study. In patients treated with trimetazidine, complications such as arrhythmia, CCF and angina after myocardial infarction were

compared with the other group who received thrombolytic therapy alone.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

One hundred patients who met criteria for acute MI during the first year of the study were enrolled in the study. All patients had a complete history of risk factors and contraindications to streptokinase use, a detailed examination and cardiac enzymes were performed; CK-MB, Trop-T and EKG were performed. Blood C / E, urine C / E, lipid profile, uric acid, and BSR were performed in all patients. Acute MI was confirmed by cardiac enzymes and changes in ECG. After confirmation, half, ie 50 patients, received streptokinase and trimetazidine as early as possible and the remaining 50 received only Streptokinase and were followed up for 6 months.

Inclusion criteria:

1. Open to all groups over 16 and both genders.
2. Patients with acute MI confirmed by ECG and cardiac enzymes

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Unstable angina
2. Patients with contraindications to SK.
3. Patients with chronic kidney disease and chronic liver disease.

RESULTS:

The study enrolled 100 patients who fully met the criteria for acute myocardial infarction. In the group of –I 50 patients were treated with thrombolytic therapy, i.e. with streptokinase alone. In group II, 50 patients were treated with streptokinase together with trimadizidine. These patients were followed up to six months, and complications such as arrhythmia, congestive heart failure, bleeding, re-infarction, angina and death were compared between the two groups. The mean age of the men ranged from 45 to 50 years as shown in Fig. The most common risk factors in Group I and II are smoking and are only found in men. Although it was high in group I, i.e. 12.5% compared to group II, i.e. 10.5%. the proportion of other risk factors such as diabetes, hypertension, hyperlipidemia and family history were the same in both Groups I and II, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Risk factors for coronary heart disease in Group-I and Group-II

Risk Factors	Group-I [n50]	Group-II [n50]
Smoking	25 (50%)	21 (42%)
Diabetes Mellitus	10 (20%)	12 (24%)
Hypertension	10 (20%)	9 (18%)
Hyperlipidemia	3 (6%)	5 (10%)
Family History	2 (4%)	3 (6%)

Acute MI occurred in 62% of men and 38% of women in Group I, while 60% men and 40% of women in group II. Consequently, the proportion of men was higher in both groups compared to women, as shown in Figure 5. Regarding complications during thrombolytic therapy and follow-up, the

ventricular arrhythmia in group I was 14%, atrial fibrillation 13%, after angina pectoris 20%. , CCF 12% and bleeding 10%, while in group II the ventricular arrhythmia was 2%, atrial fibrillation 2%, angina after MI 3%, CCF 6% and bleeding 8% as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Complications during thrombolytic therapy and follow-up period in Group-I and Group-II

Complications	Group-I (Streptokinase) [n50]	Group-II (streptokinase trimetazidine) [n50]
Bleeding during SK	5 (10%)	6 (12%)
Ventricular arrhythmia	7 (14%)	2 (4%)
Post MI angina	10 (20%)	2 (4%)
Atrial fibrillation	7 (14%)	1 (2%)
CCF	5 (10%)	2 (4%)

DISCUSSION:

100 patients who experienced an acute myocardial infarction were enrolled in this study. They were divided into two groups: I and II. Group I was treated only with thrombolytic therapy, in group II - trimetazidine with thrombolytic therapy and continued for 6 months. The rates of complications and mortality in both groups were compared. In both groups, the average age of men was 45–50 years, and of women 55–60 years. This is quite similar to other studies where the average age was 45-50 years. In our study in men, acute MI occurs at a younger age compared to other studies in Pakistan where it occurred between the ages of 55 and 64. The male-to-female ratio in our study was 1.3: 1, which is quite similar in other studies where acute MI is more common in men than in women. Why MI occurs at a young age in men may be due to the typical presentation more frequently compared to women who have the atypical picture of MI more frequently, and thus delayed diagnosis of MI in women. There was no gender difference in people over the age of 70. In terms of risk factors, smoking and hypertension were more common in Group I compared to Group II. As for complications during thrombolytic treatment and the follow-up period, bleeding in group-I occurred in 10% of patients, and in group II in 12%, which is quite similar in other

studies, where it was 15.9%. Ventricular arrhythmia in group I occurred in 12% of patients, while in group II in 4% of patients, which is significantly less than in group I, while in other studies the ventricular arrhythmia was about 8%. Atrial fibrillation in group I occurred in 13% of patients compared to 3% of patients in group II. Congestive heart failure occurred in 11% of patients in group I, and in 7% in group II. Cardiac arrest occurred in 3 patients from group I who were awakened after resuscitation, and in 1 patient from group II. Angina after MI occurred in 20% of patients in group I, which is quite similar in other studies. However, in 6% of patients in group II. Therefore, angina after MI was significantly lower in patients from group II than in group I. During the 6-month follow-up, the mortality in group I was 8%, and in group II - 4%. Therefore, in a patient who started treatment with trimetazidine together with streptokinase and continued throughout the follow-up period, angina after MI was significantly lower compared to group I, in which this method was not used.

CONCLUSION:

These results are quite similar from other studies. It was also observed that the incidence of ventricular and supraventricular arrhythmias was also significantly lower in group II patients using

trimetazidine. Long-term mortality was also lower in patients in group II compared to patients in group I.

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